

ISic3236

Inscribed funerary urn of Flavianos

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

2016.10.4

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 841

Physical Description

A rectangular white marble urn, with a lid. The lid has acroteria on each of the four corners. The urn has square fluted columns depicted in relief on each vertical corner, and a tabula ansata in light relief fills the front face.

Dimensions

Height 24 cm
Width 45.5 cm
Depth 28 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-4: 15-20 mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. Φλαβιανός · χρησ
2. τός · καὶ ἄμεν (πτος) · ἔζη (σεν)
3. ἔτη · λζ · μῆν (ας) · γ ·
4. ἡμέ (ρας) · ι ·

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Phlabianos (Flavianus), worthy and blameless, lived for 37 years, 3 months, 10 days.

Translation (it)

Flaviano, degno e innocente, visse 37 anni, 3 mesi, 10 giorni.

Commentary

According to Paolo Orsi, the urn still contained the deceased's ashes when it was discovered, and traces of gilding were still visible on some of the letters and the capital of one of the relief columns. The use of the name Flavianus suggests a date after the beginning of the Flavian dynasty (beginning with Vespasian, 69 AD), but Flavianus' status as slave, freedman, or free remains uncertain. The use of architectural elements in the form of the chest and a tabula ansata to frame the inscription are typical features of ash chests of this period.

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Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 87
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 216
Libertini, G 1937. Il Castello Ursino e le raccolte artistiche comunali di Catania.
At 50
Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 134

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